

INNOVATIVE PRACTICES IN BABED PROGRAM FOR HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER TRAINEES

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Introduction:

In order to improve teaching learning process we need to think and implement innovative practices, methods, ideas, skills and strategies for teacher training programme. This is the need of hour. Innovative practices help to explore abilities and will challenge teaching learning process of teacher trainees at each and every stage of programme.

It will make them aware about different possible ways as how to improve their skills of teaching. Some of the innovative practices that can introduce are as follows:

1. Plan teacher trainees visit in a school every month

If teacher trainees get more chance to visit in a school every month than they will understand and learn teaching learning process more easily and effectively. They should get a chance to observe school teacher's lesson and the school activities. Many schools can be selected so that each student can get a chance to visit urban, rural and semi-urban areas. If we plan like this than in one year a teacher trainee can observe at least 10 teachers from different school. This practice will help a teacher trainee to learn maximum number of teaching skills and they may understand the practical problems that teachers may encounter while teaching.

2. Allowing teacher trainees to attend school staff and PTA meeting

If teacher trainees get an opportunity to attend school staff and PTA meeting than they will able to understand the teaching profession more easily and they will develop professional ethics of a teacher. They will understand the roles and duties of a teacher in staff and PTA meetings. They will also understand how senior teachers keep their points in the meeting. In PTA meeting teacher trainees can understand how parents ask their various questions and how school teacher handles and tackle their questions in systematic manner

3. Organize school teacher's lecture in a college every month

Every month college should organize school teacher's lecture to share their experiences of school life, school environment and various problems related to students behavior, attitude, pornography, cybercrime, mobile copying etc. The school teachers are in a better position to discuss the various difficulties that they may face in teaching profession. They can highlight the key issues and topic that needs to introduce in their own subject. This practice may boost teacher trainee's confidence and may help them in their future life.

4. Every month organize headmaster/ headmistress lecture in a college

Headmaster/Headmistress can be invited to give lecture once in a month to express their views on various issues and challenges that they may face while handling the students, teachers and parents. They can talk on teaching profession, leadership skills and what are the different task they have to do and what is teacher's role in decision making and work environment. He/ she can discuss the future challenges and opportunities in school teaching profession. He/ She can be a great resource person for future teachers of India. If this practice is followed than teacher trainees will get broad ideas of their future career and they will succeed in their life. Even college can establish good rapport with school headmaster/ headmistress and this will surely help them in conducting effective practice teaching and internship in schools.

5. Every month organize alumini students lecture

When student takes an admission to first year training course that time they may find it very difficult to cope with expectations and practices of teacher training program. Few students may leave the course at the beginning as they can't adjust to the environment of the new course and college. During this difficult time if college organizes Alumni's talks than it will help and boost teacher trainees to understand this course very easily and they will get a moral support to plan their future studies in an effective manner. By this way, teacher trainees will have easy access to ask all their difficulties and queries to alumni students.

6. Teacher trainees must take interview or do case study of their school teacher who is their role model for them.

Human being always learns by imitation and observation. As a project or assignment teacher trainee must go in their own school and take the interview of the teacher who is the best as per their opinion. By this practice teacher trainee will visit their own school and meet their school teachers and will get some good guidance from school teachers. It will be second chance for them to visit their own school. When they goes to take interview of their school teacher they will interact with them by establishing good rapport with them and will understand the key qualities of their teacher which made them successful in their life. And in future teacher trainees may also try to inculcate those good qualities in them.

7. Teacher trainees must take interview of 10 teachers

As a part of internship teacher trainee should take interview of at least 10 teachers' from same or different schools. Since teacher trainees are in learning process they are in receptive mode to inculcate all the good qualities of teacher by having one to one conversation. By doing this task teacher trainees will understand how those teachers have balanced their personal, professional and social life. They will also get an idea as how to tackle the difficulties that may come in their professional life.

8. Organize workshops on:

- Personality development
- Leadership skills
- Life skills
- value education
- Event Management
- How to search books in a library
- Conducting debates
- Analysis of textbook, question papers.
- Educational Scheme

9. Organize short term course on:

- Typing
- MS office
- MS PowerPoint
- MS excel
- Techniques to search information on internet
- Educational software's (FOSS)
- Educational sites

10. Organize talks on:

- Children's right
- Importance of blood donation followed by camp.

- Biographies of some of the great teachers.
- Assignments on following topic can be given
- Case study of educational thoughts of Mahatma Gandhi, Swami Vivekananda, Rabindranath Tagore, Jiddu Krishnamurthy, Gijubai Badeka, A.P.J. Abdul Kalam.
- MOOC, FOSS, INFLIBNET,
- UGC NET, CSIR NET, SET,
- NAAC, NCTE, NCERT, SCERT, RIE
- BED, MED, MEDBED, B.SCB.ED, B.A.B.ED, M.A.EDU

11. Increasing passing percentage:

Passing percentage must be 50% for the first three years and 55% for teacher trainees of last year where they have to pass separately both in internal and external examination. This may be the turning point in the field of education and will provide quality teacher's to our nation.

It is very important that teacher educator must mould teacher trainees into the effective teacher. This is possible only when they provide enough practical experience to teacher trainees to explore their ideas and creativity. Even to prepare a gold ornament it needs to burn at very high temperature. Similarly to train effective teacher we must provide wide variety of opportunity to future teacher's of India.

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